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Perceived Influence of School Libraries in Universal Basic Education Schools: A Case Study of Junior Secondary Schools in Benue State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated the perceived effect of school libraries in universal basic education schools in Benue State, Nigeria. The study was guided by two (2) objectives and two (2) research questions. The study adopted descriptive survey research design with a population of 100 respondents made up of forty-six (46) teacher librarians, forty-six (46) head teachers and eight (8) library staff from State Universal Basic Education headquarters, Makurdi. The sample size comprises the entire population as it is relatively small and can be effectively managed by the researchers. The instrument for data collection was a questionnaire structured and designed by the researchers titled "Questionnaire on Influence of School Libraries in Universals Basic Education Schools" (QISLUBES). Data collected was analyzed using Mean and Standard Deviation and presented in tables. The finding of the study revealed that the influence of school libraries in universal basic education junior secondary schools in Benue State, Nigeria is low. The finding also revealed that there are various challenges associated with the development of school libraries in universal basic education

junior secondary schools in Benue State, Nigeria. It was concluded that school libraries in universal basic education junior secondary schools in Benue State, Nigeria, can influence both students and teachers in the schools if provided, organized and maintained. The study then recommended that the government should make plans for a well-structured and more organized libraries in schools to support universal basic education junior secondary school programmes and that professional librarians should also be employed to man the existing school libraries in other to provide quality information resources and service delivery.

Keywords: Universal Basic Education, School Library, Library and Information Science, Library Influence, Literacy

Introduction

The universal basic education programme was introduced in 1999 to enhance the provision of qualitative education by ensuring uninterrupted access to the nine-year free and compulsory basic education for every child of school age. The programme, according to Oguntuase (2014), is also meant to drastically reduce the incidences of school drop-out and engender quality assurance and efficiency in the sub-system. Above all, universal basic education is geared towards the acquisition of literacy, numeracy, life- long education and useful living.

Universal basic education in any society is important as it is the foundation of education and also helps to eradicate illiteracy and poverty. According to Moruf (2015), universal basic education in Nigeria is an educational programme that should be compulsory for all children between the ages of six and fifteen years. The author further added that it is equally geared toward consolidating literacy, numeracy, the acquisition of social and appropriate life skills. Similarly, Popoola (2011) stated that the major objectives of universal basic education are to universalize access to basic education, engender a conducive learning environment, and eradicate illiteracy in Nigeria within the shortest possible time. Thus, Universal Basic Education is the hub of national development. The idea behind the universal basic education is that, at the end of nine years of basic education, every Nigerian child would have been properly equipped to contribute meaningfully to the development and growth of his/her immediate society and this can be done by putting into action the skills acquired during the period.

The provision of library services in universal basic education schools is crucial and indispensable as school libraries are established to advance the course in these schools. School libraries are established and aimed at producing intellectually developed and complete individuals in society. The school library can be defined as the whole stock of books and other resource materials in a school. It is a collection of a wide variety of learning and teaching materials which are housed in a place and centrally organized by staff and indexed to serve users. School libraries according to Adebamowo (2011) are libraries in primary and secondary schools whose collections are mainly for young people. School libraries help children in their studies and assist teachers in their teaching and periodical research. The main objective of school libraries is to procreate an urge for reading amongst the children who get first-hand knowledge to use the library resources most effectively to further their careers. School libraries help to inculcate discipline in the child who uses it.

The objective of the school library is achieved when there are instructions on how to take care of books, maintain silence in library, and read together. In fact, the need for the school library is inevitable, making it the reason efforts are made to develop school libraries in universal basic education schools. In line with this, the universal basic education implementation guidelines emphasize that libraries have to be of the appropriate quality and size to meet the minimum standards for promoting any meaningful teaching and learning. Since the school library aids the universal basic education programme, which is an inclusive programme encompassing the formal school system from the beginning of primary education to the end of junior secondary school; there is the need for programmes and initiatives for early childhood care and socialization, education for the acquisition of functional literacy, numeracy and life skills, especially for all learners. With functional libraries, a permanent literacy experience can be established within nine years in junior secondary schools in Benue state, Nigeria. This study, therefore, set to investigate the perceived effect of school libraries in universals basic education schools in junior secondary schools in Benue State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

School libraries provide information and ideas that are fundamental to successful functioning in societies and give students lifelong learning skills, develop the imagination, citizenship, critical thinking skills, and ability to use information in different mediums. When librarians and teachers work together, students achieve more. School libraries, aside from enhancing literacy and numeracy through access to a variety of relevant learning resources, encourage sharing and caring for communal resources, just as it strengthens civic and moral values. These therefore make school libraries an integral component of the school curriculum. It has been established that students who study in a literacy-rich environment with good school libraries perform better than those who do not have this advantage.

Different researchers have conducted research to show the perceived influence of school libraries in universals basic education schools. Adebamowo (2011) carried out a study on the state of school libraries and its effect on the universal basic education programme in Ogun State, Nigeria and revealed that some of the problems of school libraries include lack of accommodation, lack of qualified personnel, lack of library facilities, lack of library resources and equipment, lack of political will and lack of government policy. Similarly, Ogwu (2010) in his study on school library development and attainment of the universal basic education objectives in Kogi State, Nigeria, revealed that school libraries provide information materials to both students and teachers, contribute to students' information literacy skills, organized literacy classes, provide mobile library services, and develop of independent learning skills.

Moruf (2015) in his study also on utilization of school libraries in Akinyele Local Government Area of Oyo State, Nigeria revealed that there were libraries in most public schools but were non-functional. His study revealed the importance of school libraries to include provision of free access to ICT, organization of literacy classes, organization of summer reading programmes, provision of literacy instructions, guaranteeing access to knowledge and impact positively on the academic achievement of the student. The study equally indicated the problems of school libraries to include among others as materials not

being up-to-date, lack of funds, lack of staff and lack of infrastructure. Ademu and Sule (2011) study on the Universal Basic Education (UBE) programme and the school libraries in Nigeria revealed that there are no functional school libraries in UBE schools in the area studied and even when they exist all the necessary facilities are not adequately provided. Their study also revealed that school libraries are very central to educational process and that school libraries help to promote the development of information literacy skills among students, improve student's literacy, enhance the spirit of enquiry and self-actualization, improve literacy, numeracy and manipulative skills.

In his study on the role of school libraries in the implementation of the Universal Basic Education (UBE) programme in UBE Junior Secondary Schools in Kwande Local Government Area of Benue State, Tondo (2012) discovered that there are no school libraries to support UBE programme in UBE junior secondary schools in Kwande Local Government Area, even where they exist are grossly understocked and manned by a non-professional. Tondo's study also revealed that provision of reading materials, development of language skills, provision of literacy instructions, promotion of independent learning, organization of book talks and promotion of reading culture are the influence of school libraries in universal basic education schools. The study equally indicated that lack of infrastructures such as building, chairs, shelves and alike, lack of financial support, unqualified personnel, lack of current library resources, lack of ICT facilities and absence of library lessons on the school lesson's timetable were the major challenges associated with the development of school libraries in universal basic education schools.

Unfortunately, the researchers have observed that almost all universal basic education schools in Benue State seem not to have functional school libraries. This could be that the renovation and construction projects in Benue State, also, seem not to consider provision of space for school libraries. Thus, non-availability of this facility might result in non-availability of teaching and learning resources which are collected and organized by school libraries for used by both teachers and students for teaching and learning process for successful attainment of the objectives of universal basic education.

Again, the researchers observed that the importance of school libraries has not been recognized due to the non-provision of functional school libraries in the universal basic education schools in Benue state and these have prompted this study. The study therefore will seek to investigate the perceived influence of school libraries in universal basic education schools: a case study of junior secondary schools in Benue state, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

- i. What is the influence of school libraries in universal basic education junior secondary schools in Benue state Nigeria?
- ii. What are the challenges associated with the development of school libraries in universal basic education junior secondary schools in Benue state Nigeria?

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive survey research design with a population of 100 respondents made up of forty-six (46) teacher librarians, forty-six (46) head teachers and eight library staff from State Universal Basic Education headquarters, Makurdi. The sample size comprises the entire population as it is relatively small and can be effectively managed by the researchers. The instrument for data collection was a questionnaire structured and designed by the study's researchers and titled "Questionnaire on Influence of School Libraries in Universals Basic Education Schools" (QISLUBES). The questionnaire was distributed by the researchers and three other research assistants drawn from the senatorial zone of the state. Data collected was then analyzed using Mean and Standard Deviation and presented on the table.

Results

Results of the study are presented according to the research questions.

Research Question One

What is the influence of school libraries in universal basic education junior secondary schools in Benue state Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation Analysis of the influence of school libraries in universal basic education junior secondary schools in Benue State Nigeria (n=100)

S/No	ITEMS	Mean	SD	Decision
1	Provision of free access to information resources	2.41	0.71	Low Extent
2	Provision of free access to Internet facilities	2.39	0.68	Low Extent
3	Organization of book talks	2.37	0.65	Low Extent
4	Organization of literacy classes	2.38	0.69	Low Extent
5	Organization of arts classes	2.33	0.75	Low Extent
6	Organization of drama	2.36	0.72	Low Extent
7	Organization of song competition	2.42	0.63	Low Extent
8	Provision of literacy instructions	2.43	0.73	Low Extent
9	Organization of summer lessons	2.41	0.70	Low Extent
10	Organization of study support programmes	2.35	0.65	Low Extent
11	Organization of discussion groups	2.40	0.69	Low Extent
12	Provision of exhibitions	2.34	0.70	Low Extent
13	Provision of literacy support services	2.45	0.72	Low Extent
14	Organization of children events	2.42	0.63	Low Extent
15	Organization of cinema or films for children	2.33	0.69	Low Extent

16	Provision of mobile library services	2.40	0.70	Low Extent
17	Conducting public enlightenment programmes	2.42	0.63	Low Extent
	Cluster Mean	2.39	-	Low Extent

Findings in Table 1 show the Mean and Standard Deviation of the influence of school libraries in universal basic education junior secondary schools in Benue State, Nigeria. As revealed on the table, the respondents rated “low extent” on all items with mean values ranging from 2.33 – 2.45 and standard deviation ranging from 0.63 – 0.75. The table also revealed a cluster mean of 2.39. With this cluster mean of 2.39 which is below the benchmark of 2.50, it can be deduced from this finding that the influence of school libraries in universal basic education junior secondary schools in Benue State, Nigeria, is low. The finding of this study agrees with the finding of Ogwu (2010) who noted that school libraries provide information materials to both students and teachers, inculcate to students’ information literacy skills, organize literacy classes, provision mobile library services and development of independent learning skills. The finding of this study also agrees with the finding of Moruf (2015) who in his study in Akinyele Local Government Area of Oyo State, Nigeria found out that there were libraries in most public schools but were non-functional and further discovered the importance of school libraries in universal basic education junior secondary schools to include provision of free access to ICT, organization of literacy classes, organization of summer reading programmes, provision of literacy instructions, guarantee access to knowledge and impact positively on the academic achievement of the student. The findings of this study are in line with Ademu and Sule (2011) study who noted that there are no functional school libraries in UBE schools and even when they exist all the necessary facilities are not adequately provided. This study corroborates with Tondo (2012) study who noted provision of reading materials, development of language skills, provision of literacy instructions, promotion of independent learning, organization of book talks and promotion of reading culture to be the influence of school libraries in universal basic education schools.

Research Question Two

What are the challenges associated with the development of school libraries in universal basic education junior secondary schools in Benue state Nigeria?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation Analysis of the challenges associated with the development of school libraries in universal basic education junior secondary schools in Benue State Nigeria (n=100)

S/No	ITEMS	Mean	SD	Decision
1	Absence of government policy on school library development	3.38	0.71	Agree
2	Lack of commitment to school libraries by government and school administrators	3.51	0.75	Agree
3	Poor educational system which is examination-oriented	3.36	0.63	Agree

4	Inadequate facilities such as chairs, tables, sheaves etc	3.45	0.61	Agree
5	Inadequate qualified librarians	3.53	0.74	Agree
6	Inadequate funds	3.45	0.60	Agree
7	Lack of ICT facilities	3.58	0.77	Agree
8	Non-inclusion of use of library in school curriculum	3.40	0.72	Agree
9	Negative attitude of school head teachers/principals on school library development	3.63	0.63	Agree
10	Lack of accommodation	3.05	0.72	Agree
11	Inadequate library resources	3.29	0.65	Agree
12	Lack of Internet connectivity	3.02	0.71	Agree
	Cluster Mean	3.39	-	Agree

Table 2 shows the challenges associated with the development of school libraries in universal basic education junior secondary schools in Benue state Nigeria. As revealed on the table, the respondents rated agree on all items with mean values ranging from 3.02 – 3.63 and standard deviation ranging from 0.61 – 0.77. The table also revealed a cluster mean of 3.39. This implies that all the items listed are agreed to be the challenges associated with the development of school libraries in universal basic education junior secondary schools in Benue State, Nigeria. The findings of this study are in line with the findings of Adebamowo (2011) who in his study revealed some of the challenges encountered in school libraries include lack of accommodation, lack of qualified personnel, lack of library facilities, lack of library resources and equipment, lack of political will and lack of government policy. The findings of this study corroborate with Moruf (2015) who in his study discovered some of the challenges of school libraries to include among others as materials not up-to-date, lack of funds, lack of staff and lack of infrastructure. The findings of this study are in line with Tondo (2012) who discovered that there are no school libraries to support UBE programme in UBE junior secondary schools in Kwande Local Government Area of Benue State, even where they exist are grossly understocked and manned by a non-professional. His study further revealed that lack of infrastructures such as building, chairs, shelves and alike, lack of financial support, unqualified personnel, lack of current library resources, lack of ICT facilities and absence of library lesson on the school lesson's timetable were the major challenges associated with school libraries, which the current study has also noted as challenges associated with the development of school libraries in universal basic education junior secondary schools in Benue State, Nigeria.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that school libraries in universal basic education junior secondary schools in Benue State, Nigeria, can influence both students and teachers in the schools if provided, organized and maintained. Though, from the findings of this study, there are no school libraries in universal basic education junior secondary schools in Benue state, Nigeria. Even where they are available, they are dilapidated and abandoned. The renovation and construction projects in Benue State, also, seem not to consider provision of space for school libraries when building schools; and this has created lots of challenges in schools in Benue State, Nigeria, today.

Based on these findings, the study recommended that:

- i. The government should make plans for a well-structured and more organized libraries in schools to support universal basic education junior secondary school programmes in Benue State, Nigeria.
- ii. Professional librarians should also be employed to man the existing school libraries in other to provide quality information resources and service delivery to students and teachers and to achieve the goals of universal basic education in Benue State, Nigeria.
- iii. The government should connect with other stakeholders in the State so as to invest in libraries and information resources and service delivery in Benue State, Nigeria.

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